

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Country Report of Costa Rica

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This Country Report is the result of intense collaborative work between the Costa Rican Institute of Sports and Recreation (ICODER) and the international cooperation consortium comprising the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University (CIDE).

The consortium especially wishes to express its gratitude to the Minister of Sport's office and the staff of ICODER, whose technical team was deeply involved and committed to developing this document.

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Introduction

By mandate of the High Authorities of Sport in Ibero-America, including Ministers, the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), have developed the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in Ibero-America. More recently, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University have also joined the Consortium.

The Ibero-American sports indicators aim to provide countries with periodic, standardized, and comparable information on the impact of sports across different dimensions of sustainable development, as well as the periodic evaluation of policies to identify opportunities for improvement and support achievements and results. Additionally, the indicators seek to facilitate the measurement of the social return on sports, ultimately promoting increased investment in sports and physical activity.

The creation of 12 indicators and four key data points for implementation in the region was unanimously approved at the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023. Additionally, it was agreed to conduct a pilot of the indicators in a group of applicant countries. The countries participating in this first stage of the pilot were Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

The pilot study, conducted between August 2023 and March 2024, aimed to validate the clarity, feasibility, thematic relevance, and cost-effectiveness of the indicators, as well as to perform an initial calculation of these indicators based on the available information sources. Additionally, it sought to generate a country report on each nation's situation and a cross-cutting document on results and lessons learned.

This document corresponds to Costa Rica's Country Report, analyzing the status of the indicators and their information sources based on the pilot study, as well as the challenges in generating them according to the country's social, cultural, and economic context. Likewise, it establishes the connection between the indicators and the policies and programs for sports and physical activity, along with the country's long-term strategic vision.

The report is complemented by technical sheets for the indicators that were successfully calculated, as well as a general manual for developing technical sheets for the indicators that could not be estimated during the pilot phase. The technical sheets provide a detailed description of the main characteristics of the indicators, facilitating their correct interpretation, implementation, and scalability. They are essential for replicating their calculation and fostering discussion among experts.

Similarly, it is also recommended to consult the Pilot Results and Lessons Learned Report, which provides an overview of the progress made by the three participating countries and presents their technical assessment of the indicators. The report also includes a list of lessons learned and recommendations for the next phases of the pilot study and the implementation of the indicators across the region, as well as the challenge of establishing homogeneous and comparable data collection criteria among countries.

The country report is the result of intense collaborative work between the Costa Rican Institute of Sports and Recreation (ICODER) and the international cooperation consortium formed by CID, UNESCO, GIZ, CAF, and the King Juan Carlos University. In particular, the consortium would like to express its gratitude to the Minister of Sport's office and the staff of ICODER, whose technical team was strongly involved and committed to the development of this document.

I. Country Context

Sports and physical activity in countries are closely linked to their social, cultural, and economic context, as well as to their visions and priority objectives outlined in their policies and strategic programs. Therefore, it is important to address the country's situation in these areas to better understand the progress and challenges in sports and the difficulties in implementing the indicators in the country, while keeping in mind that one of the main objectives of the indicators is for them to be comparable across the different countries in the region, it is also key to understand the environment in which the indicators are developed.

Costa Rica has been characterized by having Human Development Indices ranging from medium to high, which has distinguished it among the countries in the Latin American region. This has been supported by its public health systems, social security, education, community organization, and other components that have shaped a successful socioeconomic development model since the second half of the 20th century. However, this model has begun to show signs of wear in recent times. Thus, in the early decades of the 21st century, inequality has increased, socioeconomic exclusion of certain sectors, crime, the perception of public insecurity, and the once emblematic public education system have all demonstrated a profound crisis, which was exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic. These factors present new challenges for sports and physical activity as dimensions of development and as tools for achieving objectives in different areas of sustainable development, especially: health, education, inclusion, and the promotion of peace and social cohesion.

Due to the previous reasons, the promotion of opportunities for physical activity, sports, and recreation for the national population has been maintained and even strengthened, constituting a factor of integral development that the Costa Rican state has prioritized through actions such as the approval of the National Policy on Sports, Recreation, and Physical Activity (PONADRAF) 2020-2030 (ICODER and MIDEPOR, 2020) and the constitutional reform that has established physical activity as a right for the population, previously implied within the regulatory framework of the right to health.

Since the late 20th century, Costa Rica has been laying the foundations to establish community networks for the promotion of physical activity for health, a process that was consolidated with the creation of the Costa Rican Physical Activity Network (RECAFIS), coordinated by the country's Ministry of Health. This is complemented by the network of Canton Sport and Recreation Committees (CCDR), which operate in each of the country's cantons (the canton being the basic administrative unit of Costa Rica's political division), the network of Youth Committees, and other community networks that have been forming across the territory since the mid-20th century. Additionally, sports associations and federations, along with the promotion of physical education in the national education system, have been key components. The efforts of these various actors have been integrated into the Sports, Recreation, and Physical Activity System (DRAF), with the Costa Rican Institute of Sports and Recreation (ICODER) being a key institution in managing these processes.

As part of the implementation of the PONADRAF, Costa Rica has prioritized the management of programs and projects with an emphasis on Results-Based Management. In this framework, within the DRAF System, it is essential for ICODER to lead by example, striving for better coordination among the organizations belonging to the DRAF System.

The implementation of the Pilot Plan for the Ibero-American Indicators of Sports and Development has allowed ICODER to practically assess the realities it must face to meet the needs of the population and build a baseline of indicators for future management.

Additionally, the country has managed to incorporate the DRAF agenda into its long- and medium-term planning instruments through goals and indicators in the National Strategic Plan 2030-2050 (PEN), linking the Sustainable Development Goals and the Montevideo Consensus on Population and Development (CdM), as well as in the National Development and Public Investment Plan 2022-2026 (PNDIP), the National Health Policy 2023-2033 (PNS), the National Policy for Children and Adolescents 2024-2036 (PNNA), and the Public Policy for Youth 2020-2026 (PPPJ).

II. Indicator Creation Process

The process of creating indicators, from the mandate for their creation at the XXVIII General Assembly of CID to the presentation of pilot results within the framework of the XXX Assembly, has spanned a two-year period of various activities.

Figure 1 outlines the timeline of the main political and technical milestones that have occurred during this period, culminating in the present Country Report for Costa Rica.

Figure 1. *Timeline of the Indicator Creation Process*

An important aspect to highlight is that the current set of 12 indicators and four key data points is the result of a broader set of 60 indicators that was used as discussion material in an extensive participatory analysis process in the region. This process included the application of an online exploratory questionnaire with the participation of 83 specialists from different fields; 18 semi-structured interviews with experts from academia, government representatives, and international organizations; two focus groups with 22 government representatives; and a preliminary validation virtual meeting in November 2022. This event involved 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region. Additionally, technical validation was carried out by the governments of the region during the seminar: “Plan for the creation of sports indicators in sustainable development in Ibero-America,” held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia in March 2023.

Based on the above, the implementation of 12 indicators and four key data points was approved at the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, as well as the implementation of a pilot program of indicators in a group of applicant countries.

In this way, in June 2023, the Consortium launched a call to the CID countries to participate in the pilot study based on certain basic technical criteria and institutional commitments for the applicant countries. After analyzing the applications, the following month, the interested countries were informed that the pilot, in its first phase of implementation, would include the participation of Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

III. General Progress Overview

From a general perspective on the progress in calculating the indicators, Costa Rica was able to implement all four key data points and four of the 12 indicators (33.3%). A summary of these advancements is shown in Table 2, where, in addition to the value of the key data point or indicator, some important observations are also presented in the third column, which will be addressed in more detail in the following sections.

Table 1. Results of the Implementation of Key Data Points and Indicators in the Pilot

Key Data Point	Value	Observations
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Autonomous Body	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	
Indicator	Value	Context
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	No value	Greater intersectoral coordination is needed to achieve its calculation.
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	No value	It is necessary to have a satellite account for its calculation.
3. Percentage of the population over 19 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age*	63.9%	Value not comparable with that of other countries.
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	11.4%	Value generated externally by GOPA
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	No value	
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	No value	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	No value	
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	36.4%	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 19 years old*	15.3%	Value not comparable with that of other countries.
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	No value	It is necessary to form intersectoral technical teams.
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	No value	It is necessary to have a survey for its calculation.
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	No value	

Note: * The indicator is not comparable with other countries because there are no complete information sources that allow verifying that the same concepts and criteria for data collection and processing are applied.

IV. Situation of Key Data Points and Indicators

This section presents the situation of the value of the key data points and indicators, regardless of whether it was possible to calculate their value during the pilot study. For each key data point and indicator, a brief justification or relevance for its calculation is provided, along with its basic features. Subsequently, the country's position regarding the situation of the indicators and the policies or strategic actions it is currently implementing or plans to implement to strengthen its compliance are presented.

The value of the key data points and indicators is considered preliminary in the sense that they are the result of a pilot study aimed at providing more elements to strengthen the accuracy of calculation methods, the validity and transparency of information sources, and, above all, to initiate processes of standardizing information to ensure the comparability of indicators at the regional level. In this sense, at the moment, several indicators are not strictly comparable between countries because the information provided by the countries is not sufficiently complete to conduct a detailed analysis of the comparability of the indicators and their explanatory factors.

The details for calculating the indicators, as well as the concepts used, can be consulted, for indicators with a value, in the technical data sheets document for the country; and for indicators without a value, in the general guide for the preparation of technical data sheets. The main fields of information contained in the technical data sheets are: indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, frequency, geographical coverage, information sources, and concepts used, among others.

Key data point I. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.

Key data point with value

To support the design of policies and programs for sport and physical activity with evidence, it is essential to have representative, reliable, and periodic data. Having a national survey on sports practice and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is the first step in building basic indicators in this area, such as the percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active and the existing gaps by gender or age groups.

The value of the key data point in Costa Rica regarding whether there is a national survey no older than five years on the practice of sport and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is "partially." This is because the reference survey is older than 5 years, it is not representative for the population groups under 18, 18 to 64, and over 65 years old, and the survey's methodological design, microdata, and basic tabulations are not directly available to the public.

Table 2. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	2018	Caja Costarricense de Seguro Social (2018)

Country's Positioning

The study of physical activity, sport, and recreation habits of the Costa Rican population officially began in the 1970s, when the first surveys were conducted with adolescent populations regarding their recreational practices. However, it wasn't until the 1990s that surveys with representative samples of the country's population began to be conducted on this phenomenon. Since then, data has continued to be collected on physical activity habits, sedentary time, and participation in sport and recreation, through various surveys and with different methodologies.

Since 2010, the Costa Rican Social Security Fund (CCSS) has been conducting a survey every four years using an internationally standardized methodology to record the level of physical activity related to health in the adult population. This survey has provided data in 2010, 2014, and 2018, although the fourth round was delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. While the CCSS survey is the most suitable for describing the physical activity habits of the population, it does not cover topics related to sports practice and recreation. As a result, efforts have been made by ICODER to conduct a national survey that can better address these issues. The implementation of this survey (ICODER's first national survey) in 2022 marked a key challenge for the institution and the DRAF sector, positioning the need for more strategic alliances in the use of public spaces and establishing in the Costa Rican imagination the programs and projects offered to the population to meet the objective outlined in the ICODER Creation Law. It also aimed at promoting, supporting, and encouraging the individual and collective practice of sports and recreation for the citizens of the Republic.

Key data point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity

Key data point with value

The governmental rank of the national governing body of sport and physical activity determines its ability to establish regulations, design policies, implement programs, and manage resources. Therefore, it is a key data point to establish the rank of the national governing body of sport and physical activity in the country.

It is considered that the most appropriate governmental rank for the national governing body of sport and physical activity should be that of a ministry or an entity with a high degree of autonomy and powers similar to those of a ministry.

The governmental range of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in Costa Rica is that of an autonomous institution.

Table 3. Basic features of key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Autonomous Body	2024	Asamblea Legislativa de Costa Rica (1998)

Country's Positioning

According to the national regulatory framework, ICODER's semi-autonomous status allows it to develop technical proposals and manage public budgets with a medium- and long-term vision, facilitating the consolidation of nationally impactful programs and fulfilling the constitutional right to sport, recreation, and physical activity. However, it is crucial to strengthen this semi-autonomy with a broader budget allocation and greater agility in the management and use of resources. Additionally, it is important to increase the number of staff hired by the institution to provide the various services demanded by the sector's governance in a regionalized manner.

This will allow ICODER to maximize its effectiveness and efficiency in implementing policies and programs aimed at promoting sport and physical activity in the country, thereby ensuring a greater impact on society and a better response to the needs of the population.

Key data point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.

Key data point with value

"Each education system must assign the requisite place and importance to physical education, physical activity and sport in order to establish a balance and strengthen links between physical activities and other components of education. It must also ensure that quality and inclusive physical education classes are included, preferentially on a daily basis" (UNESCO, 2015a, p. 3).

Thus, there is a need for data or indicators that allow us to assess countries' commitment to promoting physical education in early childhood—a stage that, as widely documented, is critical for shaping habits and lifestyles in adulthood.

In Costa Rica, physical education is a mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level. However, it is not an independent subject, nor is the number of hours per week clearly specified in the curriculum (at least not in the document presented as evidence). Therefore, the value of the key data point is considered "partially".

Table 4. Basic features of key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	2024	Asamblea Legislativa de Costa Rica (1998)

Country's Positioning

Among the actions required to consolidate broader coverage of the DRAF sector, it is necessary to engage with the Ministry of Public Education and the central government regarding the need to complete the hiring of physical education teachers in primary and secondary schools to ensure that 100% of schools and colleges in the country have coverage of this subject. As of 2023, only 59.7% of schools and 84.19% of colleges had assigned physical education teachers, with coverage being worse in public educational institutions (59.21%) compared to private and subsidized ones (97.49%), despite public institutions serving the majority of the student population (89.10% of the national enrollment).

Therefore, the first step should be to ensure the universalization of physical education at all levels of formal education, as required by the country's legislation since 1998. After that, strategies should be implemented to increase the number of minutes per week for this subject. In Costa Rica, only 80 minutes per week are taught, typically in a single session, in centers with assigned teachers for this subject.

Key data point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

Key data point with value

Legal frameworks are of relevance as they express fundamental principles and rights of individuals, as well as priorities and the scope of objectives, strategies, and programs. This highlights the importance of having data on the existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity.

To establish the existence of such legal frameworks and ensure that they are effectively applied, it is necessary to present evidence that the legal instruments have been used to design policies, programs, or actions with concrete results to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity.

In Costa Rica, there are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and supervise gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity. Similarly, there is evidence that these legal frameworks are applied and used to design policies and programs with concrete results.

Table 5. *Basic features of the key data point*

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ministerio del Deporte de la Asamblea Legislativa de Costa Rica (2021) •Instituto Costarricense del Deporte y la Recreación, ICODER (2023) •La Gaceta, Diario oficial de Costa Rica (2023)

Country's Positioning

In Costa Rica, there is still room for improvement in creating clear and specific legislation that promotes gender equality and prohibits discrimination in sports and physical activity, including sanctions for those who fail to comply with these principles.

In addition, it is necessary to promote awareness and training on gender equality among sports stakeholders, ensuring the equitable participation of women and men in all sports instances.

Similarly, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be established to oversee compliance with regulations and promote role models that encourage diversity and inclusion as fundamental values in this field.

Indicator I. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity

Indicator without value

The allocation of the budget to sports and physical activity is an objective measure of the importance given to the sector in public investment priorities, and at the same time, a concrete reference regarding the scope of policies in terms of available resources.

A limitation of the indicator is that it does not record the budget for sports and physical activity allocated to government offices outside the national governing entity in the field. Therefore, it is desirable that in the future, a broader indicator be developed to more accurately capture the number of public resources allocated to the sector.

Table 6. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

One of the main challenges in Costa Rica's public policy is ensuring that sports and physical activity are prioritized in the government's budget allocation. This requires raising awareness every four years among the authorities about their importance as tools for social development, health, well-being, and social peace.

Meanwhile, continuous improvement in the management of ICODER becomes a key factor in strengthening its political negotiating position and ensuring a more generous budget allocation from the central government to uphold the fulfillment of a constitutional right. This process should include the promotion of legislative improvements for the allocation of resources dedicated to the objectives and actions proposed by ICODER.

However, the participation of a variety of actors in this process has generated challenges in obtaining clear and precise inputs, which has limited the ability to gather data effectively as planned. Overcoming this structural limitation will be crucial to optimizing the effectiveness of sports and physical activity policies and programs in the country.

Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP

Indicator without value

Sports and physical activity have a significant impact on multiple sectors and economic activities, but due to the lack of measurements or information records, this impact has not been adequately recognized or valued. Therefore, having statistics on the contribution of sports and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) would help highlight their impact, understand their relationship with other sectors or economic activities, and also support the design of policies and programs.

Despite its importance, having this indicator presents considerable challenges for countries due to the technical complexity of its calculation and the financial needs to create its information sources. The ideal information source for this indicator is a satellite account for sports and physical activity. A satellite account is a national accounting tool that records in an organized, systematic, and complete manner all the transactions carried out by the economic agents of a country related to a specific sector or activity, in this case, sports and physical activity.

A satellite account typically takes three to four years from its conception to its execution and generation of results. Therefore, it was not the objective of the pilot to calculate this indicator, but rather to familiarize countries with the scope and requirements of a satellite account.

Without the need for a satellite account, it is possible to provide approximations of the contribution of sport and physical activity to GDP. However, these data are not as precise and detailed and require making multiple assumptions. For example, all the countries in the European Union have data on the contribution of sport and physical activity to GDP, but less than half of the countries within the EU have a satellite account for sport.

Table 7. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The ICODER, as the governing body of the DRAF sector until 2023, has begun the necessary efforts to construct the Satellite Account for Sport. This project is currently under development and has even involved the request for personnel to be dedicated to it. The implementation of this satellite account will be essential for obtaining accurate and up-to-date data on the contribution of sport and physical activity to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This process will facilitate better measurement and monitoring of the economic and social impact of sport, which will help guide policies and programs more effectively, as well as strengthen the sports industry in Costa Rica.

Indicator 3. Percentage of the population over 19 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age

Indicator with value

Regular physical activity is one of the most important mechanisms for the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and several types of cancer. Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health, as it prevents cognitive decline and symptoms of depression and anxiety (WHO, 2020). Therefore, it is crucial to have indicators on the percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active.

At the same time, given the different needs of individuals and the existing inequalities between them, it is important to break down the indicators by age, sex or gender, ethnic origin, or socioeconomic status, among other factors. This approach helps to make visible the inequalities and inclusion challenges that should be addressed by sports and physical activity policies.

In Costa Rica, the percentage of the population over 19 years old who are sufficiently physically active is 63.9%.

It is important to note that the value of this indicator will be comparable across different countries in the region to the extent that the sources of information and methodologies used are complete and similar. Alternatively, a prior statistical standardization exercise could have been carried out. However, given the scope and complexities, this was not addressed in the first phase of the pilot. Initially, none of the countries provided complete methodologies, questionnaires, coding manuals, or microdata from the surveys used as sources of information. Therefore, it is likely that the countries are using different methods to account for the time dedicated to sport and physical activity, but due to the lack of information, it is not possible to determine this.

The above implies that the indicator for Costa Rica should not be considered comparable to that of other countries, at least not until more complete information sources are available from the countries and an appropriate process of statistical standardization has been carried out.

The comparability of indicators between countries is undoubtedly one of the most challenging complexities that must be addressed to implement the indicators validly and effectively at the regional level.

Table 8. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the population over 19 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age	63.9%	2018	Caja Costarricense de Seguro Social (2018)

Country's Positioning

As mentioned earlier, Costa Rica has research processes on the physical activity habits of its population, with a national survey focused on health issues (the one conducted by the Costa Rican Social Security Fund, an ally of the DRAF sector in health matters), which serves as the primary source for this indicator. This survey has sustainability, ensuring future availability of data with the same methodology. Since the formulation of ICODER's national survey in 2022, the institution has gathered new inputs and data on DRAF practices. However, the first exercise of that survey involves improving the data collection tools and mechanisms, which will require assigning more financial resources to fund the project for 2025.

Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old

Indicator with value

According to the WHO (2022), "Physical inactivity is one of the leading risk factors for noncommunicable diseases mortality. People who are insufficiently active have a 20% to 30% increased risk of death compared to people who are sufficiently active."

Therefore, it becomes essential to have indicators on deaths related to physical inactivity that allow quantifying the magnitude of the problem for each country, and from this, implement policies to address it.

The percentage of deaths due to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years of age in Costa Rica is 11.4%.

Table 9. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	11.4%	2021	Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021)

Country's Positioning

Similarly, ICODER will seek to continue its national survey by improving its methodology and strengthening partnerships with research teams from the academic units of the country's public universities that offer programs in the field of Human Movement Sciences, all within the same framework established by PONADRAF, to improve this aspect.

Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education

Indicator without value

"Physical education is the most effective means of providing all children and youth with the skills, attitudes, values, knowledge and understanding for lifelong participation in society" (UNESCO, 2015b, p. 6).

For this reason, it is important to know the percentage of primary and secondary schools that offer the minimum number of minutes of physical education. To have a reliable indicator, it is desirable that it be the result of a school census, or if not possible, a representative survey. Currently, Costa Rica lacks enough information to establish the value of this indicator.

Table 10. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

As previously mentioned, in Costa Rica, only 80 minutes of physical education are taught per week in schools and high schools according to the guidelines set by the Ministry of Public Education (MEP) since the 20th century, and it is unlikely that the MEP will increase this number in the short term. Therefore, significant advocacy will be required to persuade MEP authorities to agree to such a fundamental change. However, as also mentioned earlier, the priority at this time must be to achieve the universalization of physical education lessons in primary and secondary schools across the country. ICODER, together with other organizations in the DRAF system, will continue to pursue these efforts.

Indicator 6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator without value

The effectiveness of policies for sports and physical activity in education should ultimately be reflected in the proportion of sufficiently active students, especially at the basic education level, as this is where important lifelong habits are formed. This underscores the importance of having such an indicator. Additionally, it is crucial to break down the indicator by gender, as female students have historically faced greater setbacks compared to their male peers in various aspects of development, including sports and physical activity.

Table 11. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of school students sufficiently active stratified by gender	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

In addition to what was previously stated, it is necessary to resume studies with representative samples of schoolchildren regarding their physical activity habits and sedentary time. The only research conducted in the country with a representative sample of this population dates back to the 1996-1997 period. Since then, only some sporadic surveys have been conducted with secondary school students. ICODER, together with other actors in the DRAF system, will continue efforts to promote a specific survey on this phenomenon for this population sector, which is also part of the actions to be completed within the framework of PONADRAF.

Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs

Indicator without value

In the budgets of public entities and their objectives, the political and programmatic priorities of the government are reflected, and therefore, they constitute an objective measure to assess the government's efforts to close the gender gaps in sports and physical activity.

To establish the proportion of the budget focused on gender-specific programs, it is necessary for these programs to have explicit and verifiable objectives and actions aimed at closing the gender gaps.

Table 12. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

To strengthen the compliance of the indicator, it is crucial to consider implementing measures such as establishing budget quotas exclusively dedicated to initiatives that promote gender equality in sports and ensuring their effective allocation.

Additionally, monitoring and follow-up mechanisms should be established to verify the proper use of these funds and their impact on promoting gender equality in sports. These actions should be carried out in collaboration with civil society and other stakeholders, promoting transparency and accountability in the management of resources allocated to gender programs in sports.

Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity

Indicator without value

In leadership positions within public or private organizations, one of the most significant gaps between women and men is observed. This highlights the importance of monitoring the situation and progress towards gender equality in leadership roles within national entities for sports and physical activity. Based on this information, it will be possible to support better policies or affirmative actions in this area.

In Costa Rica, 36.4% of leadership positions in the national sports entity (Ministry of Sports) are held by women, indicating that gender equality between men and women still faces significant challenges to overcome.

Table 13. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	36.4%	2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instituto Costarricense del Deporte y la Recreación ICODER (2024a) • Instituto Costarricense del Deporte y la Recreación ICODER (2024b)

Country's Positioning

To improve the results of this indicator, it is advisable to consider establishing gender quotas in selection and promotion processes, as well as ensuring a transparent and equitable recruitment process that promotes gender diversity in leadership teams.

Additionally, it is essential to develop training and mentorship programs aimed at women interested in taking on leadership roles in sports, providing them with the necessary tools and skills to succeed in these positions. Furthermore, an inclusive organizational culture should be promoted that values and recognizes the contributions of women at all levels of the sports entity, fostering a work environment that supports their professional development and advancement within the organizational hierarchy.

Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 19 years old

Indicator with value

There are notable differences in the level of physical activity between women and men, particularly, "the data shows that in almost all countries, girls and women are less active than boys and men" (WHO, 2020, p. 2). In fact, it can also be observed in most countries in the region that the gender gaps increase significantly with age.

One of the most important objectives of sustainable development is to eliminate gender gaps or differences in their multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is crucial that governments and the general public have indicators that allow them to monitor their progress toward reducing or eliminating gender gaps in physical activity between men and women.

The percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 19 years old is 15.3%. Considering that a positive percentage gap means that the proportion of women sufficiently physically active is lower than the corresponding proportion of men, significant gender equality challenges are inferred for this indicator.

As with Indicator 3, it should be assumed that Costa Rica's indicator is not comparable to those of other countries, at least until more complete sources of information from the countries are available and a proper process of statistical data standardization has been conducted.

Table 14. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 19 years old	15.3%	2018	Caja Costarricense de Seguro Social (2018)

Country's Positioning

ICODER, along with other entities of the DRAF system, particularly through its collaboration with RECAFIS, will continue advocacy efforts to ensure that research on the physical activity habits and sedentary time of the Costa Rican population continues to be conducted with a standardized and scientifically valid methodology. Additionally, the institution, along with these other entities, will persist in generating actions aimed at closing the gender gap in this indicator. This also aligns with the actions to be carried out within the framework of PONADRAF.

Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities

Indicator without value

The Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities establishes that, in order for people with disabilities to participate on an equal footing in recreational, leisure, and sports activities, countries must adopt measures to encourage and promote the participation of people with disabilities in sports activities, ensure they have the opportunity to organize and develop sports and recreational activities, and guarantee their access to sports facilities (UN, 2008).

To put into practice what is established in the Convention, it is necessary to allocate public funds to programs aimed at enabling people with disabilities to access sports and physical activity. Similarly, it is essential to invest in data and indicators with the purpose of measuring whether this objective is being achieved.

Table 15. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

With improvements in the efficiency and management of ICODER, there is an opportunity to negotiate a larger budget allocation for inclusive sports programs, including those aimed at people with disabilities.

This capacity to manage allocated resources more efficiently will allow for the support of a broader sector of the population and the development of sports programs tailored to the specific needs of people with disabilities. The modification of instruments, internal regulations, and ICODER's structure has laid the groundwork for more effective, results-oriented management, which will facilitate the promotion of inclusion in the sports sector.

Indicator II. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population

Indicator without value

People with disabilities are one of the population groups with the greatest delay in access to development under equal circumstances. For this reason, the way to verify whether policies or programs aimed at the population with disabilities are effectively achieving results is to observe whether their physical activity and sports gaps compared to the rest of the population are decreasing.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have representative surveys on the physical activity levels of the disabled population, including disaggregation by age, sex, or gender, that allow capturing differences or levels of inclusion within the group.

Table 16. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The generation of research processes on physical activity habits and sedentary time in the population living with disabilities in Costa Rica, involving representative samples of this population, is a national challenge. As part of the actions required by PONADRAF, this challenge is one of many that must be addressed in the medium term. ICODER, along with other entities in the DRAF sector, will continue its advocacy efforts to make this happen, seeking to engage various actors from other institutions who will need to commit to achieving this goal.

Indicator I2. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence

Indicator without value

Sports overcome geographical, social, and political barriers; connect people, communities, and countries; and in this way, promote coexistence and social and political inclusion.

Sport for development and peace is conceived as a social intervention strategy that, using games, physical activity, and sports, addresses explicit objectives of peace and development. This perspective "incorporates issues such as gender equality, the promotion of peaceful coexistence, fostering tolerance for differences, encouraging inclusive behaviors, conflict prevention, and promoting health and well-being" (GIZ, 2021).

Therefore, the relevance of generating indicators on related topics is clear, but at the same time, it presents a challenge for countries due to the technical complexity involved in designing reliable, accurate, and transparent indicators.

Table 17. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The integration of peace and coexistence approaches into government sports programs represents a key challenge in promoting values of tolerance and inclusion in Costa Rican society.

The ICODER's involvement in managing new institutional database models for the administration of programs and projects represents a significant advancement, although the construction and contracting of these databases require extended periods. With the designation and hiring of staff to manage the databases for institutional programs, the aim is to strengthen the management and monitoring capacity of government sports programs, which will facilitate the integration of peace and coexistence approaches into these initiatives, thus contributing to the promotion of a culture of peace and development through sport.

V. Lessons learned

Based on the results and observations during the pilot implementation, the following are some of the most relevant findings and lessons learned for Costa Rica:

- It is essential to improve coordination with the Ministry of Finance to generate budgetary information about the ICODER budget and the amounts allocated by other government sectors in the field of sport and physical activity. More effective coordination will also be key to carrying out the process of creating a satellite account for sport and physical activity in a more valid and effective manner.
- In addition to political commitment for the implementation of the indicators, it is necessary to allocate significant resources for the creation of specialized technical teams, trained and with available time and resources to carry out the technical and operational activities required for the execution of the pilot study.
- The lack of complete information sources, both for the indicators that could be calculated and for those that could not, is a significant limitation in generating representative and comparable indicators across countries in the region. Specifically, for indicators resulting from surveys, it was not possible to obtain complete methodologies, questionnaires, coding manuals, and microdata. Therefore, it is not possible to determine with certainty the degree of comparability of Costa Rica's indicators with those of other countries.
- The generation of indicators and the creation of their information sources requires multidisciplinary and intersectoral work teams to understand and operationalize concepts. From this, better conditions will be created for the understanding, calculation, and monitoring of the indicators.
- The measurement and policy monitoring capabilities of governments can be substantially improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers. In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, these partnerships would ensure some continuity in the generation of information and the monitoring of indicators.
- Having reliable, periodic, and relevant information and indicators requires investment from both the government and society as a whole. Specifically, for the calculation of certain indicators, the government needs to allocate budgetary resources for the creation of new representative surveys, satellite accounts, or administrative records. Similarly, investment is required to develop the capacity for data collection, indicator creation, and evaluation and monitoring mechanisms.

To obtain a more general view of the findings and lessons learned for all the countries participating in the pilot and the international cooperation consortium, it is recommended to consult the general document on results and lessons learned, which emphasizes the challenges related to the sufficiency of information sources, the comparability of indicators between countries, and recommendations for the following phases of the pilot study.

VI. Recommendations and Next Steps

To implement all the Ibero-American indicators with greater validity and comparability, and to continue strengthening the measurement and information generation capabilities for designing evidence-based policies, the following recommendations are provided for the country:

- Formation of an intersectoral (sports, health, finance, economy, national statistics) and interdisciplinary working group for the technical analysis of the indicators and the mapping of sources of information and indicators on sports and its impact on development, as well as for proposing policies and technical criteria for the generation and standardization of statistical information in the field.
- Establish a working mechanism with a local university for the joint development of the indicators and to build measurement capacities in the public sector related to sports and physical activity. One of the main activities of this working mechanism will be to contribute to the process of standardizing statistical information in Costa Rica based on the guidelines set out in the general technical sheets of the indicators, whose results will allow for valid and reliable comparability of the indicators across different countries.
- In coordination with the intersectoral working group and the international collaboration consortium, establish a work plan to create the information sources for the indicators that could not be calculated during the pilot. The work plan should include work schemes and responsibilities for the different types of actors, potential funding sources, and work schedules.
- Given the limited availability of information, even for the indicators that were successfully calculated, it is necessary to create a work plan to make complete and detailed methodologies, questionnaires, coding manuals, and microdata from the currently available representative surveys accessible to the public. In addition to ensuring greater transparency, this would allow the Consortium to establish better mechanisms for standardizing the information resulting from different countries in the region.
- Design a strategy for monitoring and tracking the indicators, which, in addition to implementing the baseline for all the indicators, includes a first follow-up report to observe the evolution of the indicators. The strategy should also include preliminary goals for the indicators.
- Hold working sessions with experts to establish an initial set of goals for the indicators.
- Promote international cooperation mechanisms to share experiences, knowledge, and training.
- Seek partnerships with financial institutions or international investment funds focused on highlighting inclusion gaps in access to sports and the development of women, people with disabilities, indigenous populations, and people in poverty through reliable indicators and statistical information.
- Invest heavily in human resource training for the generation of indicators and monitoring and evaluation systems on the impact of sports on development.

Conclusions

The four key data points and four out of the 12 indicators were calculated, which is considered a limited performance since at least half of the indicators could not be estimated as initially planned in the pilot study. Additionally, even for the indicators that were successfully calculated, it is necessary to improve the accuracy and transparency of the information provided. However, the objective of identifying challenges and opportunities for the implementation of the indicators in the country and the necessary requirements to ensure their comparability with indicators from other countries in the region was met.

Given the innovativeness of the indicators, not only for the Ibero-American region but also globally, the process for their construction and implementation must be gradual and well-documented, with spaces for technical reflection and also for assessing their policy implications and international cooperation.

It is considered key for Costa Rica to establish multidisciplinary and intersectoral technical teams to improve information sources and have more accurate analyses to assess the situation of the indicators and their use to support policies.

Costa Rica's experience in the pilot study has been valuable as it allowed for mapping information, identifying challenges, locating opportunities, and preparing the working teams for the general implementation of the indicators in the near future. At the same time, its experience will serve as a reference for the countries that will participate in the following phases of the indicators pilot, helping them advance more effectively in their own indicators.

Finally, the pilot study has allowed different specialists in sports and physical activity from Costa Rica and the region to come together, which could serve as the beginning of the formation of the multisectoral and interdisciplinary teams required by the indicators for their understanding and calculation. At the same time, this could lead to broader bilateral and multilateral cooperation projects, strengthening the transfer of knowledge in Ibero-America on measurements and indicators to support policies and achieve results in sports and sustainable development.

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